

Future disease prediction based on existing health status using Machine Learning

Anilect Jose

PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala

anilectjose2022a@mca.ajce.in

Binumon Joseph

Asst. Professor of

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala

binumonjosephk@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract - In each year many different types of new diseases are spreading all over the world, each of them are coming with different symptoms. Many people are not that much bothered about them till they got affected and admitted in the hospital. And many of this happens because of fewer knowledge about diseases and seriousness, this may also lead to death also. So as a solution, people can use this application to find the disease and it's seriousness by providing their health status and other details. For this we use here four different machine learning algorithms and find the common accurate data from them.

Keywords – disease, symptoms, python, machine learning, flask, health status, prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

From this 2019 we have faced one of the biggest pandemic situation which is named as Covid-19. This disease have spread all over the world within few days. It was showing some symptoms like cough, fever, headache, body pain, etc. But there also we have normal diseases which have same symptoms, so it was so complicated to sort out which one was it until shown in hospitals, which is also risky. This review is concerned with the prediction of upcoming disease which will be affecting to the a person with the help of their current health status. Here we will take their age, gender and some symptoms which they currently feeling. By this data it will be used to clean a dataset where it contains collection of symptoms. This will help the user to sort out what is their real disease and what will be the quick solution to avoid them to affect them. Also if it is more dangerous then a doctor's detail will be recommended to the users.

For a accurate solution here we use four different machine earning algorithms: K-NN, Naive Bayes, Random Forest and Decision tree. Each algorithms will be check the dataset of diseases and symptoms for the count of disease occurrence. From the above four algorithms Naive Bayes and Random Forest will give the best accurate values than other two algorithms by using the training and test dataset. Then from the four results a common solution will be shown as the final predicted solution.

With the help of the above result of predicted disease, we can check that persons health status and provides a simple solution. This will be calculated with the help of their age and gender collected on starting and the open-source dataset. Finally by a accurate values and solutions there is a dataset which help to recommend a doctor for a specific disease that we predicted. This will make a big change in medical department, many problems will be solved by this study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mohammad Shabaz and Urvashi Garg in their paper future disease using health status using link prediction, in this research uses the rapid link prediction technique (SULP) to anticipate future diseases based on present health care and how long the link will survive. The probability score $P(k)$ for each k connection is used to determine relationships between items in any system. This helps in lowering referral traffic and disease overlaps, which reduces the isolation of a node from the network. SULP assists us in quickly determining the link between nodes while maintaining a high level of accuracy.

Mark Woolhouse in his work how to make predictions about future infectious diseases risks said that if an infectious illness is present, how rapidly will it spread, how many people or animals will be afflicted, and how long will it persist? If humans or animals are to be treated, vaccinated, or isolated in an attempt to limit an epidemic, how many, how chosen, and how soon? Everything is be

Irfan Ullah Khan, Sumayh S. Aljameel, Nida Aslam, Eman S. Asulmi and Malak Aljabri in their study Machine Learning-Based Model to Predict the Disease Severity and Outcome in Covid-19 patients, they used supervised machine learning algorithms to investigate the influence of vital signs, chronic illness, early clinical data, and demographic factors on the mortality and survival of COVID-19 patients. The dataset has data imbalance since the COVID-19 patients had a lower death risk. To correct the data imbalance, the SMOTE method was applied. Using 10-fold cross-validation, the findings indicated that random forest outperformed the other models. For parameter optimization, a grid search approach was used. The accuracy of the research was 0.952, and the AUC was 0.99.

Darcy A. Davis, Nitesh V. Chawla, Nicholas Blumm, Nicholas Christakis and Albert-László Barabási in their paper Predicting Individual Disease Risk Based on Medical History is describing the vast range of techniques established for forecasting the risk of various diseases, such as heart disease, hepatitis, Alzheimer's disease, and so on. Our method is special in that we are attempting to develop a generic prediction system that can make use of a larger feature space, such as all available demographics and past medical history. Furthermore, rather than specialized test findings, we depend on ICD-9 insurance codes to make forecasts that account for past medical history.

Goh et al. (2007): the disorder–gene connotation and finds the origin of many diseases along with a vital role of the disease gene in the human interactome.

III. MOTIVATION

Nowadays there we see new different variety of diseases are been affected to people. All of them are showing a symptom which make the disease different from others. These diseases can be damage our organs and health which may also lead to death also. Some people will consult with doctors and get medicines, but many of them will avoid this things assuming that it's normal and consulting is a waste of time. Some disease like Covid will be destroy smelling abilities and taste of food, but they can be cured if we find the correct disease before it will do everything.

By using some dataset and 4 different machine learning algorithms we find a solution for this issue. We can make assurance of a specific disease and find the easiest solution for that by providing the exact symptoms that we have. This will also recommend a doctor for this disease. For making more sure, there will be shown the other symptoms that may come when this disease will affected.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

Tools & Processing

Python:

Python is a general-purpose, high-level, interpreted programming language. It priorities code readability and makes considerable use of indentation in its design philosophy. Python is garbage-collected and dynamically typed. There it contains many libraries and many algorithms, few of them are using here.

Naive Bayes:

Naive Bayes classifiers are a type of "probabilistic classifier" based on Bayes' theorem and strong (naive) independence assumptions between components (see Bayes classifier). They are one of the most basic Bayesian network models, but when combined with kernel density estimation, they can achieve great levels of accuracy. Here we get the user input and find the accuracy value from it.

K-NN:

K-nearest neighbors is type of supervised machine learning algorithm and calculate the distance of a new data point to all other training data points. Input values will be predicted and accuracy value will be accrued.

Random Forest:

It's based of concept of ensemble learning, which is a process of combining multiple classifiers to solve a complex problem and to improve the performance of the model. Same as the above algorithms, this find the accuracy score of predicted disease.

Decision Tree:

It is a tree-structured classifier, where internal nodes represent the feature of a dataset, branches represent the decision rules and each leaf node represent the outcome.

Flask

Flask is a Python-based micro web framework. It is referred to as a micro framework since it does not necessitate the usage of any specific tools or libraries. It lacks a database abstraction layer, form validation, and other components that rely on third-party libraries to accomplish common tasks.

V. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is work based on a specific methodology.

Step by step process:

Step 1: Inserting symptoms/diseases with their age and gender, then request for the result.

Step 2: Cleaning of the dataset will be done, and from that training and test dataset will be created.

Step 3: Inserted data will be taken to python code and each symptoms will checked through the four algorithms: Random Forest, K-NN, Naive Bayes and Decision Tree.

Step 4: After all four algorithms used, we will find the common solution with the accuracy of each one and stored to variable.

There is many chance that different disease will be predicted by these algorithms, but Naive Bayes and Random Forest is having priority.

Step 5: With the predicted disease from each algorithms we will recommend a doctor using a open-source dataset and will find the status and solution for the disease using the other dataset which have ages and gender.

Step 6: All above results will be returned from the function and sent back to the web page and displayed. This all will be with respect to inputs user gives.

Fig 4.1 Flowchart of methodology

VI. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the in any Machine Learning Algorithm. The steps involved in model building are as follows:

1. Importing packages that needed

```

1 from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
2 from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
3 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
4 from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
5 from sklearn.naive_bayes import MultinomialNB
6 from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
7 from sklearn import tree
8 import csv, numpy as np, pandas as pd
9 import os
  
```

Fig 5.1: Packages used

2. Read all data from the csv files

```

1 data = pd.read_csv(os.path.join("Training.csv"))
2 data2 = pd.read_csv(os.path.join("DoctorDataset.csv"))
3 df = pd.DataFrame(data)
4 df2 = pd.DataFrame(data2)
5 cols = df.columns
6 cols = cols[:-1]
7 x = df[cols]
8 y = df['prognosis']
9 x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(x, y, test_size=0.33)
  
```

Fig 5.2: Using CSV files

3. Fitting using different algorithms

```

1 gnb = MultinomialNB()
2 gnb=gnb.fit(x_train,np.ravel(y_train))
3
4 knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=3, metric='minkowski', p=2)
5 knn = knn.fit(x_train, np.ravel(y_train))
6
7 clf3 = tree.DecisionTreeClassifier()
8 clf3 = clf3.fit(x_train,y_train)
  
```

Fig 5.3: Fitting of train data

4. Checking the accuracy using test data set

```

1 print("Naive Bayes")
2 print("Accuracy")
3 disease2 = gnb.predict(user_input_label)
4 print(disease)
5 y_pred1 = gnb.predict(x_test)
6 naiveacc = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred1)
7 print(accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred1))
8 print(accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred1, normalize=False))
9 disease1 = disease[0]
10 disease3 = disease2[0]
  
```

Fig 5.4: Accuracy using Naive Bayes

We also use 3 other algorithms to find the best accurate prediction of diseases.

5. Sorting and finding the status and best solution

```

1 age = int(age)
2 df1 = df[(df.age1 <= age) & (df.age2 >= age) & (df.gender==gen) & (df.disease==mx)]
3 st=list(df1['status'])
4 sol=list(df1['solution'])
  
```

Fig 5.5: Packages used

VII. RESULT

The results shows the accuracies, obtained by applying the three Machine Learning algorithms (Radom Forest, K-NN, Naive Bayes and Decision Tree). The result also provides the current status of person and a simple solution to avoid that.

Fig 6.1: UI of Disease prediction

```
<class 'bytes'>
Counter({'Allergy': 3, 'GERD': 1})
Allergy
Dr Krishna Sah
10 male
```

Fig 6.2: Result from all algorithms

VIII. CONCLUSION

Every life of the human is very important one who cannot recreate a life, so here in this study we are predicting the upcoming disease with current health status of the person. This make more accurate prediction because we use four different machine learning algorithms and also collecting all types of information that needed like age and gender. This will be predicting the exact disease with same symptoms and gives a status and solution about that predicted disease. This will help people to take a precaution on their health status and maintain a health.

IX. REFERENCE

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